

LEADERSHIP COMMUNICATION AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the correlation of leadership communication and students' academic performance, focusing on four dimensions such as clarity, depth, care, and responsibility. Using a quantitative research approach, the study analyzes the relationship between school leaders' communication practices and students' academic achievements, measured through grade point averages (GPA). The findings provide insights into how effective leadership communication fosters a supportive learning environment, enhances student engagement, and ultimately improves academic performance. The study also offers recommendations for educational leaders to implement communication strategies that promote student success. Findings indicate that both teachers and school heads demonstrated strong leadership communication, particularly in terms of responsibility. Despite these, the study found a statistical difference between teachers' and school heads' leadership communication levels, indicating variations in communication approaches between the two groups. Furthermore, the correlation analysis revealed no relationship between leadership communication and students' academic performance, suggesting that other factors may play a more influential role in shaping student outcomes.

Keywords: *Leadership Communication, Academic Performance, School Heads, Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the cornerstone of development in any society, and effective communication plays a pivotal role in shaping the academic landscape (Zardari & Ali, 2023). In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, the role of leadership communication in shaping students' academic performance is important. Schools are complex structures in which student achievement and educational quality are directly impacted by interactions among leaders, teachers, students, and other stakeholders. The ability of school leaders to convey their vision, objectives, and expectations is at the heart of this dynamic. Fostering academic excellence requires an atmosphere of trust, enthusiasm, and shared purpose, all of which may be achieved through effective leadership communication. Effective communication by school leaders is a systematic process of engagement that fosters collaboration, forges relationships, and empowers all stakeholders. It goes beyond simply sharing information. Leaders who communicate clearly and inclusively create a supportive and accountable culture that improves teacher effectiveness and, eventually, student learning results.

According to Leithwood et. al (2020) in their review of the international evidence about school leadership, they conclude that school leadership has a significant effect on features of the school organization, which positively influences the quality of teaching and learning. While moderate in size, this leadership effect is vital to the success of most school improvement efforts. Also, school leadership is where the head teacher steers the school community, made up of teachers, learners, and parents, to achieve the set goals and objectives by persuasion and participation until the targets become a reality (Northouse, 2019).

The Department of Education has stepped out of its box from a centralized educational system that believed one size fits all, to make education very important to society, particularly to learners. According to the 2001 Republic Act 9155, known as the Governance of Basic Education Act, it seeks to improve school-based management by devolving education governance to its educational stakeholders. They serve as a critical answer to the persistent challenges the school system faces, particularly in terms of high dropout rates, quality educational service, high repeat levels, and limited school holding ability. (Alvarado 2019)

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has also emphasized school leadership as an important agent in achieving the Education 2030 Agenda. School leadership has emerged as a key policy priority in line with the new vision for education articulated in the fourth Sustainable Development Goal, to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Evidence from research, changing and complex expectations about the school system, and the imperative to improve education quality have initiated the shift in focus from investing in teacher training, learning materials, equipment, and facilities to strengthening school governance, management, and leadership. (Shulla et. al, 2020)

According to Strait (2020), leadership and management are similar in many ways as they both work with people and influence them to complete a goal. Both are essential to the success of an organization. Requiring a need for adequate management and leadership skills, even though both differ in several ways. Management skills are concerned with planning, organizing, and controlling the mission following a rigid schedule. Leaders are more open-minded in their ideas and are more involved with their followers. They like to influence big changes and go for long-term goals. Leaders in high-performing schools take their responsibility seriously and share their experience with their subordinates, treating them as equals, which leads to a school culture that promotes effective learning and professional development (Jarl et al., 2021).

Globally, effective school leaders manage the school environment well, involve students in academic planning and decision making and encourage the cooperation and motivation of teachers and students, which are common cultural practices that are important for students' performance (Brinia et al., 2022; Sabanci et al., 2016; Tangidy & Rini, 2020).

Bush (2020) states that it's about effectively engaging and inspiring individuals and teams through communication. Various theories provide frameworks and perspectives for navigating complex organizational environments, building relationships, and achieving desired outcomes. One such theory is transformational leadership, which emphasizes the power of communication in inspiring and motivating followers to surpass expectations and achieve exceptional results. Moreover, communication theories underscore the significance of active listening and constructive feedback in leadership and management.

This research aims to examine how leadership communication influences students' academic performance. It seeks to analyze the effects of different communication practices used by school leaders, exploring whether clarity, depth, care, and responsibility in communication can enhance student outcomes. This research will offer insights and recommendations for effective strategies that promote academic achievement.

The researcher chooses to study the impact of school leaders' communication on students' academic performance because of the critical role communication plays in shaping a school's culture, environment, and outcomes. Effective leadership communication fosters a shared vision, motivates stakeholders, and builds trust, which are essential for creating a supportive learning environment. Given the direct and indirect influence school leaders have on both teachers and students, understanding how their communication practices impact academic success is a vital area of inquiry.

Research Questions

This study seeks to determine the relationship between leadership communication on students' academic performance and develop an enhancement program relative to leadership communication and students' academic performance.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of:
 - 1.1 Clarity
 - 1.2 Depth
 - 1.3 Care, and
 - 1.4 Responsibility?
2. What is the academic performance of the students in the first and second quarters?
3. Is there a difference between the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads?
4. Is there a correlation between the level of leadership communication and students' academic performance?
5. Based on the results of the study, what enhancement program anchored on leadership communication and students' academic performance may be proposed as an offshoot of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized quantitative research methods to emphasize objective measurements, or the numerical analysis of data collected through survey questionnaires. The researcher used descriptive research design that aims to describe the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads and students' academic performance accurately and systematically. Quantitative methods with a descriptive design are effective in objectively measuring variables and analyzing data through surveys (McMillan & Schumacher, 2020).

The research study employed survey research method to know how school administrators and teachers work together in achieving improved students' academic performance. The method was used to appraise the effectiveness, relevance, and adequacy of the leadership communication in meeting their school objectives.

The study utilized a correlational research design. A correlational research design is a type of non-experimental research method used to examine the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design helps determine whether a relationship exists, the direction of the relationship (positive or negative), and the strength of the association. However, it does not establish causation, meaning it cannot prove that one variable directly causes changes in another, only that they are related in some way.

In this study, the leadership communication of teachers and school heads was correlated with student performance. Leadership communication includes factors such as clarity, depth, care, and responsibility. Student performance has been measured using

academic achievement indicators like the students' first and second quarter grades. By using a correlational research design, the study analyzed the extent and nature of this relationship, providing insights into how communication strategies in leadership impact educational outcomes.

Research Locale

Cabuyao Integrated National High School in the City of Cabuyao, Laguna, served as the study's research location. This public secondary school was selected as the setting for the study because of its varied student body, faculty, and administrators, which offers a representative sample for leadership communication dynamics. The school is a perfect place to look into how leadership communication practices affect academic performance because of its organizational structure and continuous initiatives to promote community involvement.

By concentrating on one location, the study hopes to obtain knowledge that is pertinent to the local educational environment and might also be useful for comparable schools in the area, increasing the findings' generalizability.

Instrumentation

A survey questionnaire was used to collect all the information needed for this study. The researcher chose this instrument since it is the most effective technique to collect data from the respondents. This study instrument was used by the researcher to make the data that will be gathered more manageable. The survey questionnaire was validated by three experts in education and research methodology to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. Based on their feedback, revisions were made to improve question clarity and structure. After re-evaluation, the refined questionnaire was approved for use with the 27 teachers and 4 school heads.

In addition, the researcher's respondents applied Cronbach's Alpha to measure the reliability and accuracy of findings. Below is the scoring system for the level of leadership communication for teachers and school heads.

The instruments on Clarity, Depth, Care, and Responsibility reached excellent reliability ($\alpha > 0.955$). Similarly, the ordinal alpha values for Clarity, Depth, Care, and Responsibility were all greater than 0.980, implying that each construct was very highly reliable. McDonald's omega ($\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3$) values are all close to or greater than 0.957, confirming the strength of internal consistency. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are all above 0.941, which indicates that each construct catches a high proportion of variance relative to measurement error, indicating strong convergent validity. In simple words, the instruments on all constructs reached excellent reliability and very high validity, as to internal consistency and convergent validity, respectively.

Table 1
Pilot Testing Result

Reliability indices

Variable	α	Ordinal α	ω_1	ω_2	ω_3	AVE
Clarity	0.947	0.986	0.957	0.957	0.965	0.941
Depth	0.960	0.990	0.986	0.986	1.031	0.986
Care	0.965	0.993	0.984	0.984	1.012	0.983
Responsibility	0.955	0.986	0.970	0.970	1.010	0.963

Data Gathering Procedure

This research followed a systematic and well-structured approach to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and integrity of the findings. It began with the careful planning of the data collection process, starting with obtaining the necessary approvals. The researchers prepared a formal request letter and an informed consent form, which were submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent of the City of Cabuyao. These documents outlined the study's objectives, methodologies, and ethical safeguards. Upon receiving approval, the researcher finalized the tools and resources required for data collection.

The next step involved the development and validation of the research instrument. A self-made questionnaire was designed to address the specific objectives of the study, particularly leadership communication and students' academic performance. To ensure the accuracy and relevance of the questions, the instrument was subjected to validation by three field experts. A pilot test was also conducted with a small group of respondents outside the study population. Insights from this pilot test allowed the researcher to refine the questionnaire, improving its clarity and reliability. With a validated instrument in hand, the researchers moved to the sampling phase. Employing a stratified random sampling method, they ensured a representative distribution of respondents across different subgroups of the target population, which included the teachers and school heads.

The researcher distributed the survey forms to the selected respondents. Clear instructions were provided to guide the teachers and school heads, and any clarifications regarding the questionnaire were promptly addressed. Respondents were assured of the confidentiality of their answers, in line with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The researchers ensured that sufficient time was given for respondents to complete the survey accurately. Once the completed questionnaires were collected, the researchers carefully reviewed and organized the responses. The data were encoded into a digital database for systematic analysis. Statistical treatments, including descriptive statistics, Mann-Whitney U, and Spearman rho, were applied to analyze the data. These tools enabled the

identification of patterns, relationships, and significant differences, providing a deeper understanding of leadership communication and students' academic performance.

Interpreting the results was another critical stage. The findings were examined about the study's objectives and the research's theoretical framework. Insights were compared with existing literature to contextualize the results and highlight their contribution to the field of study. Throughout the data-gathering journey, ethical considerations were upheld at every step. The researchers ensured that participants' identities remained confidential and that their participation was voluntary. Transparency and honesty guided the reporting of results, reflecting the study's commitment to academic integrity and meaningful contribution to the understanding of teachers' and school heads' leadership communication.

Statistical Treatment

1. Descriptive Statistics

The researcher utilized descriptive statistics such as mean, median, mode, and standard deviation to summarize and describe the data collected from respondents: clarity depth, care, and responsibility, also the academic performance of the students in first quarter and second quarter.

2. t-tests

The researcher used the Shapiro-Wilk test to assess the normality of the data, specifically for the variable measuring the level of leadership communication. This test was conducted separately for each group (e.g., teachers and school heads) to determine whether the distribution of scores met the assumption of normality required for parametric tests. The results of the Shapiro-Wilk test indicated a significant deviation from normality ($p < .05$) in at least one group, suggesting that the data were not normally distributed.

As a result, the researcher employed the Mann-Whitney U test to compare the level of leadership communication between the two independent groups (e.g., teachers vs. school heads). This non-parametric alternative to the independent samples t-test was selected because it does not require the assumption of normality and is suitable for ordinal or non-normally distributed interval data. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference in leadership communication scores between the two groups.

3. Correlation Analysis

The researcher employed the Doornik-Hansen test to assess multivariate normality of the dataset, particularly focusing on the leadership communication variables (clarity, depth, care, and responsibility) and the students' academic performance metric (GPA). The Doornik-Hansen test was selected because it is a robust test for evaluating the assumption of multivariate normality, which is critical in determining the appropriate

statistical methods for further analysis. The results indicated that the data violated the assumption of multivariate normality ($p < .05$).

Given the non-normal distribution of the variables, the researcher used the Spearman rank-order correlation (Spearman's rho) to analyze the strength and direction of the relationship between each leadership communication variable—clarity, consistency, and frequency—and students' academic performance (measured by GPA). Spearman's rho was deemed appropriate because it is a non-parametric measure of correlation that does not assume normal distribution and is suitable for ordinal and non-normally distributed interval data.

The following tables show the guide for interpretation used in the analysis of the data.

Table 2
4-point Likert Scale and Verbal Interpretations for the Level of Leadership Communication

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Level of Assessment</i>
3.26-4.00	Very High
2.51-3.35	High
1.76-2.50	Moderate
1.00-1.75	Low

The questionnaire applied a 4-point Likert scale to measure the degree of agreement or disagreement with statements. The table on the next page was used in determining the Leadership Communication Level of Teachers and School Heads in Cabuyao Integrated National High School.

Table 3
Numerical Grade, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation for Students' Academic Performance

Correlation Interval	Verbal Interpretation
0.00	No Correlation
0.01-0.20	Very Low/Weak Correlation
0.21-0.40	Low/Weak Correlation
0.41-0.60	Moderate Correlation
0.61-0.80	High/Strong Correlation
0.81-0.99	Very High/Strong Correlation
1.00	Perfect Correlation

The grading scale in Table 3 categorizes students' academic performance based on their numerical grades and provides a corresponding descriptive equivalent and interpretation. Students who score between 90 and 100 are classified as Outstanding (O), indicating that they have exceeded the expected learning standards. Those who fall within the 85 to 89 range receive a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating, demonstrating that they have not only met but also surpassed the required competencies. A grade between 80 and 84 corresponds to a Satisfactory (S) rating, meaning the student has adequately met the learning standards. Meanwhile, students scoring 75 to 79 are rated as Fairly Satisfactory (FS), signifying that they have only partially met the learning standards. Finally, students who score below 75 fall into the Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME) category, indicating that they have failed to achieve the minimum required competencies and may need intervention or remediation to improve their academic performance. This grading system provides a clear and structured assessment of students' learning progress, helping educators identify those who need additional support.

Table 4

Interpreting Correlation between the Level of Leadership Communication and Students' Academic Performance Values Guide

Numerical Grade	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
90-100	Outstanding (O)	The student has exceeded the expected learning standards.
85-89	Very Satisfactory (VS)	The student has met and surpassed the required competencies.
80-84	Satisfactory (S)	The student has adequately met the learning standards.
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)	The student has partially met the learning standards.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations (DNME)	The student did not meet the minimum required competencies and may need intervention or remediation.

This table provides a guide for interpreting correlation values. Based on this, the Spearman correlation coefficient (-0.1501) from your previous analysis falls within the 0.01-0.20 range, which is categorized as "Very Low/Weak Correlation." This supports the conclusion that there is no strong relationship between Academic Performance Progress and Teachers' Leadership Communication Levels.

RESULTS

1. What is the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of:

1.1 Clarity

Table 5

Result in the Teachers and School Heads Level of Leadership Communication in terms of Clarity

	TEACHERS		SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS AND SCHOOL HEADS	
	Weighted Mean	SD	Weighted mean	SD	Grand Weighted Mean	SD
1.1 CLARITY						
1.1 Clearly communicate expectations and instructions	3.63	0.62	3.75	0.43	3.69	0.60
1.2 Ensure that communication is straightforward and avoids ambiguity.	3.56	0.63	3.75	0.43	3.65	0.61
1.3 Provide detailed explanations to prevent misunderstandings	3.59	0.62	3.75	0.43	3.67	0.61
1.4 Adapt communication style to meet the diverse needs of teachers/students	3.59	0.56	3.50	0.50	3.55	0.55
1.5 Regularly check if instructions or messages are understood.	3.59	0.56	4.00	0.00	3.80	0.54
Composite Mean	3.59	0.60	3.75	0.43	3.67	0.58

Legend. 3.26-4.00: Very High, 2.51-3.25: High, 1.76-2.50: Moderate, 1.00-1.75: Low

1.2 Depth

Table 6

Result in the Leadership Communication of Teachers and School Heads in terms of Depth

2. DEPTH	TEACHERS		SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS AND SCHOOLHEADS	
	Weighted Mean	SD	Weighted mean	SD	Grand Weight	

					ed Mean	SD
2.1 Provide in-depth explanations to help teachers/students fully understand tasks or concepts.	3.59	0.56	3.75	0.43	3.67	0.55
2.2 Encourage discussions to explore topics more thoroughly.	3.63	0.55	3.75	0.43	3.69	0.54
2.3 Communicate with relevant examples and supporting details.	3.70	0.53	3.75	0.43	3.73	0.52
2.4 Address complex issues or topics with patience and clarity.	3.56	0.57	3.75	0.43	3.65	0.55
2.5 Take time to engage in meaningful conversations when required.	3.67	0.54	3.75	0.43	3.71	0.53
Composite Mean	3.63	0.55	3.75	0.43	3.69	0.54

Legend. 3.26-4.00: Very High, 2.51-3.25: High, 1.76-2.50: Moderate, 1.00-1.75: Low

1.3 Care

Table 7

Result in the Leadership Communication of Teachers and School Heads in terms of Care

	TEACHERS		SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS AND SCHOOLHEADS	
3. CARE	Weighted Mean	SD	Weighted mean	SD	Grand Weighted Mean	SD
3.1 Communicate with empathy and consider the feelings of teachers/students.	3.74	0.52	3.75	0.43	3.75	0.51

3.2 Actively listen to concerns raised by teachers/students	3.63	0.67	3.75	0.43	3.69	0.65
3.3 Prioritize creating a supportive and trusting communication environment.	3.74	0.52	3.75	0.43	3.75	0.51
3.4 Follow up when they need additional support.	3.59	0.68	3.75	0.43	3.67	0.66
3.5 Communicate genuine concern for teachers' professional growth and well-being/ students' academic and personal growth.	3.70	0.66	3.75	0.43	3.73	0.63
Composite Mean	3.68	0.62	3.75	0.43	3.72	0.60

Legend. 3.26-4.00: Very High, 2.51-3.25: High, 1.76-2.50: Moderate, 1.00-1.75: Low

1.4 Responsibility

Table 8

Result in the Teachers and School Heads Level of Leadership in terms of Responsibility

4. RESPONSIBILITY	TEACHERS		SCHOOL HEADS		TEACHERS AND SCHOOLHEADS	
	Weighted Mean	SD	Weighted mean	SD	Grand Weighted Mean	SD
4.1 Ensure that important information is communicated promptly and accurately.	3.70	0.53	3.67	0.47	3.69	0.53
4.2 Take accountability for any communication lapses or misunderstandings.	3.56	0.63	3.67	0.47	3.61	0.62
4.3 Make sure to follow up on commitments and promises made to them.	3.70	0.53	3.67	0.47	3.69	0.53
4.4 Consistently provide updates and reminders to keep them informed.	3.67	0.54	3.67	0.47	3.67	0.54

4.5 Maintain transparency and openness in communication practices. 3.63 0.55 3.67 0.47 3.65 0.55

Composite Mean 3.65 0.56 3.67 0.47 3.66 0.55

Legend. 3.26-4.00: Very High, 2.51-3.25: High, 1.76-2.50: Moderate, 1.00-1.75: Low

2. What is the academic performance of the students in the first and second quarters?

Table 9

Results in the Students' Academic Performance for the First and Second Quarter

Quarter	Mean Grade	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
First Quarter	85.5	Very Satisfactory (VS)	The student has met and surpassed the required competencies.
Second Quarter	86.7	Very Satisfactory (VS)	The student has met and surpassed the required competencies.
Overall Mean	86.1	Very Satisfactory (VS)	The student has met and surpassed the required competencies.

Legend: 90-100: Outstanding, 85-89: Very Satisfactory, 80-84: Satisfactory, 75-79: Fairly Satisfactory, below 75: Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 10

Results in the Difference Between the Level of Leadership Communication of Teachers and School Heads

p-value	alpha	Decision	Interpretation
0.00006	0.05	Reject Ho	There is a significant difference

Table 11
Result in the Correlation Between the Level of Leadership Communication and Students' Academic Performance

rho-value	rho-interpretation	p-value	alpha	Decision	Interpretation
-0.1501	Negative Very Low Correlation	0.5305	0.05	Failed to Reject Ho	There is no significant correlation

DISCUSSION

1. What is the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of:

1.1 Clarity

Table 5 on the next page presents the results of the leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of clarity. The findings indicate that both groups demonstrated a very high level of clarity in their communication, with teachers obtaining a composite mean of 3.59 and school heads achieving a slightly higher composite mean of 3.75. The grand weighted mean for both groups combined is 3.67, which falls under the "Very High" descriptive category.

School heads consistently showed higher mean scores compared to teachers across most indicators, particularly in clearly communicating expectations and instructions, ensuring straightforward communication, providing detailed explanations, and regularly checking if instructions or messages are understood. Notably, school heads achieved the highest mean score of 4.00 in regularly checking for understanding, highlighting their strong emphasis on ensuring effective communication.

On the other hand, teachers scored slightly higher in adapting communication styles to meet diverse needs, indicating their responsiveness to the varied backgrounds of students and colleagues. The relatively low standard deviations suggest that responses were consistent among participants.

Overall, these results underscore the importance of clarity in leadership communication, which plays a critical role in minimizing misunderstandings, promoting collaboration, and supporting school success. The findings further affirm that clear communication practices are essential for effective leadership and contribute significantly to creating a positive and efficient learning environment.

There is enough research evidence that teacher clarity causes various positive academic outcomes, such as students' increased motivation, classroom engagement, participation, attendance, critical thinking, empowerment, and

immediacy (Finn and Schrod, 2012; Titsworth et al., 2015; Bolkan, 2017; Zheng, 2021). Also, when team members communicate clearly and openly, they can understand common goals, individual tasks, and expectations. This reduces the potential for misunderstandings and ensures that all team members have the necessary information to work effectively (Ngath et al., 2024).

Through clear and open communication, principals and teachers can ensure each team member understands their goals and tasks, build trust, and create a positive and collaborative climate. In addition, good communication also facilitates the process of receiving constructive criticism and sharing innovative ideas that can improve the quality of educational programmes and activities. (Hajjaj, 2024)

1.2 Depth

Table 6 presents the results of the leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of depth. The findings show that both teachers and school heads demonstrated a very high level of communication depth, with a composite mean of 3.63 for teachers and 3.75 for school heads. The grand weighted mean for both groups combined is 3.69, indicating a very high rating overall. School heads consistently scored slightly higher across all indicators, suggesting a strong commitment to providing thorough and meaningful communication. The highest grand weighted mean was found in communicating with relevant examples and supporting details (3.73), emphasizing the importance of context and clarity in ensuring understanding. Teachers and school heads also scored highly in encouraging discussions to explore topics more thoroughly (3.69) and in taking time to engage in meaningful conversations (3.71), both crucial for deepening comprehension and fostering critical thinking.

Meanwhile, the indicator with the relatively lower, though still very high, mean was addressing complex issues with patience and clarity (3.65), highlighting a potential area for further strengthening. The relatively low standard deviations suggest consistency in responses across participants. Overall, these results highlight that both teachers and school heads highly value depth in communication, recognizing it as essential for facilitating deeper understanding, encouraging engagement, and promoting a more thoughtful and responsive school environment.

Active listening, which involves teachers paraphrasing students' words to validate their feelings and show understanding, without judgment, is used to connect to learners and lead them to find solutions to their problems. (Karasova & Nehyba, 2023)

According to Pardo-Cueva et.al (2019), successful school management was positively influenced by the headteachers' communication skills in most public schools. Recent studies have categorized leadership communication into open, transparent, and directive approaches, each with distinct effects on stakeholder

engagement. Research shows that open and transparent communication fosters a sense of trust and encourages higher parental and community involvement (Smith & Doe, 2021).

1.3 Care

Table 7 presents the results of the leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of care. The findings show that both teachers and school heads demonstrated a very high level of care in their communication practices, with a composite mean of 3.68 for teachers and 3.75 for school heads. The grand weighted mean is 3.72, which is categorized as "Very High." Among the specific indicators, both groups scored highest in communicating with empathy and considering the feelings of teachers and students (grand mean of 3.75), as well as prioritizing the creation of a supportive and trusting communication environment (grand mean of 3.75).

These results reflect the strong emphasis both teachers and school heads place on building emotional connections and trust within the school community. Meanwhile, the lowest, though still very high, mean was found in the indicator "follow up when they need additional support," with a grand mean of 3.67. This suggests that while both groups are attentive to support needs, there may still be room for improvement in consistently following through. The low standard deviations indicate that participants responded with a high level of agreement, reflecting consistent perceptions across respondents. Overall, the results highlight the vital role of care in leadership communication, underscoring the importance of empathy, active listening, genuine concern, and consistent support in fostering a positive, growth-oriented environment for both teachers and students.

Even though teacher–student relationships are integral aspects of any learning environment, the process of creating and maintaining a positive interpersonal relationship is a demanding task even for many experienced teachers (Stranchan 2020). School principals are expected to be able to communicate well, listen empathetically, and provide constructive feedback to teachers who tend to have higher levels of trust and participation (Saniyah, Kholisah, Sya'adah, & Asy'ari, 2023).

Communication also creates interactions between principals and teachers, and these interactions leave an impression on both parties. Therefore, school principals need to understand the importance of effective interpersonal communication to create a good work environment and support teacher professional growth (Limbong, Turnip, & Situngkir, 2023).

1.4 Responsibility

Table 8 presents the results of the leadership communication of teachers and school heads in terms of responsibility. The findings reveal that both groups

demonstrated a very high level of responsibility in their communication, with a composite mean of 3.65 for teachers and 3.67 for school heads. The grand weighted mean for both groups combined is 3.66, which falls within the "Very High" category.

Teachers and school heads showed consistently strong performance across all indicators, particularly in ensuring that important information is communicated promptly and accurately (grand mean of 3.69) and in following up on commitments and promises (grand mean of 3.69).

Meanwhile, the indicator "take accountability for any communication lapses or misunderstandings" registered the lowest grand mean of 3.61, though it still falls within the very high range, suggesting a slight opportunity for further enhancement in acknowledging and addressing communication issues. The low standard deviations across items indicate a high level of consistency in the participants' responses.

Communication in learning plays a very important role in determining how the learning process takes place and its impact on students and teachers (Winata, 2021; Prijanto & De Kock, 2021). The significance of communication in education does not stop at the flow of information, but it also allows the establishment of relationships that enhance the comprehensive achievement of education (Krauter, 2022).

Responsibility in leadership communication entails accountability and ethical practices that build organizational trust. Hsieh, Song, and Li (2024) analyzed the relationship between distributed leadership and instructional quality in Taiwan, finding that teacher autonomy and innovativeness mediate this relationship. This suggests that responsible leadership practices that empower teachers contribute to improved instructional quality.

2. What is the academic performance of the students in the first and second quarters?

The results of the students' academic performance for the first and second quarters indicate that they have consistently demonstrated a "Very Satisfactory (VS)" level of achievement. In the "first quarter", the computed mean grade was "85.5", signifying that, on average, students met and even surpassed the required competencies. In the "second quarter", there was a slight improvement, with the mean grade increasing to 86.7, showing a continued positive trend in student performance. The "overall mean grade of 86.1" confirms that students maintained a "Very Satisfactory" level throughout both grading periods.

This suggests that the majority of students have successfully grasped the learning standards, demonstrating strong academic performance and steady

progress. However, there is still room for growth, and further enhancement in instructional strategies could help students reach the “Outstanding (O)” level.

The learning process is greatly influenced by the quality of communication that occurs in the classroom. If communication goes well, then learning objectives can be achieved more effectively. Effective communication is a link between the message the teacher wants to convey and the understanding received by students (Annastasya & Romadhan, 2024).

The leadership behavior of teachers directly influences students' motivation and academic performance. Igwe and Ligaya (2023) investigated how English teachers' leadership behaviors affect students' performance in the language. The study found that both consideration and initiating structure behaviors positively relate to students' integrative and instrumental motivation, which in turn enhances their English performance.

3. Is there a difference between the level of leadership communication of teachers and school heads?

Since the p-value (0.00006) is less than the alpha level (0.05), we reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This means there is a statistical difference between the two groups. In other words, the observed differences in the data are unlikely to be due to random chance, indicating that the two groups have significantly different distributions.

Schools may have stronger communication skills than teachers due to their managerial roles, training and experience. Teachers and school heads may use different communication strategies based on the responsibilities while school heads focus on school management.

Studies such as those by Anderson & Baker (2019) reveal that school heads typically engage in more formal, high-level communication, while teachers focus on the practicalities of classroom management and student engagement, leading to a discrepancy in communication effectiveness and priorities.

According to Ng, Ho, and Low (2020), school leaders must exhibit a high level of strategic communication to influence not only teachers but also parents, students, and community stakeholders. This multi-level communication responsibility often requires principals to be more formal, persuasive, and politically aware compared to teachers, whose communication is more instructional and relational.

Similarly, Zheng, Yin, and Liu (2021) found that principals' leadership communication significantly impacts school climate and teacher motivation, while teachers' leadership communication mainly affects student engagement and

classroom environment. This suggests different scopes and impacts of communication between the two roles.

4. Is there a correlation between the Level of Leadership Communication and Students' Academic Performance?

The results of the Spearman's rank correlation test, with a rho-value of -0.1501 and a p-value of 0.5305, indicate a very weak negative and statistically insignificant relationship between the two variables under study. Since the p-value exceeds the standard significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting that there is no meaningful correlation between the variables.

The findings suggest that the factor being measured, such as leadership communication, may not have a relationship on the outcome variable, like student academic performance. This highlights the need to consider other influential factors that may better explain variations in student outcomes, such as teaching quality, instructional methods, or learning environments. It also underscores the importance of adopting a more comprehensive approach when evaluating the effectiveness of educational leadership, rather than assuming a direct causal relationship based on individual components.

A study by Zellweger et al. (2020) concluded that while leadership communication is crucial for organizational success and teacher satisfaction, it doesn't always translate into direct improvements in student achievement. The study emphasized that teacher-focused leadership is important, but other factors, such as teacher training, pedagogy, and classroom management, have more direct impacts on student outcomes.

5. Based on the result of the study, what enhancement program anchored on leadership communication and students' academic performance may be developed as an offshoot of the study?

Based on the study results, an Enhancement Program for Leadership Communication is proposed to strengthen the link between effective school leadership and improved student academic performance. These findings suggest that an Enhancement Program for Leadership Communication is not just beneficial, but necessary to achieve sustainable improvements in student outcomes. This action plan focuses on developing clear, responsible, and collaborative communication strategies among teachers, head teachers, assistant principals, and principals to create a supportive learning environment that fosters student academic success.

Recent studies emphasize the critical role of leadership communication development programs in improving school performance and student outcomes. A growing body of research suggests that enhancing communication competencies among educational leaders — including teachers, head teachers, assistant

principals, and principals — directly influences the creation of supportive, high-performing learning environments.

According to Sun and Leithwood (2022), professional development programs focusing on leadership communication significantly boost the leaders' ability to foster collaboration, clarity, and trust within schools. Their findings show that targeted communication training not only improves leadership practices but also correlates with higher student academic achievement through better instructional support and motivation. Similarly, a study by Boylan and Demack (2020) emphasized that schools implementing structured communication enhancement initiatives experienced improvements in teacher morale, school climate, and student performance. They argue that leadership development must focus on interpersonal, strategic, and digital communication skills to be effective in today's educational settings.

Furthermore, Lai and Hallinger (2023) found that leadership communication practices that emphasize clarity, responsibility, and collaboration among all school actors (not just top leaders) produce a ripple effect, promoting collective efficacy that leads to better student academic performance.

Enhancement
Program

Empowering Educators: Communication for Teachers' *Workshop*

DATE
TIME

PLACE
VENUE

Angela Fae C. Santiago

Enhancement Program

Programme Rationale:

- Effective communication is a vital skill for teachers, not only in delivering lessons but also in inspiring students, engaging with parents, and collaborating with colleagues. This program aims to enhance leadership communication skills among teachers, enabling them to foster positive relationships, lead with confidence, and drive educational success.

Definition of Terms

- Leadership Communication – The ability to convey messages effectively to inspire, guide, and influence others within an educational setting.
- Clarity in Communication – The ability to convey information in a straightforward, concise, and understandable manner, ensuring that the message is interpreted correctly by the receiver.
- Active Listening – A communication skill that involves fully concentrating, understanding, responding, and remembering what is being said.
- Constructive Feedback – Providing information to individuals that helps them improve performance while maintaining a positive and supportive environment.
- Constructive Feedback – Providing information to individuals that helps them improve performance while maintaining a positive and supportive environment.
- School-Wide Communication Code of Conduct – A set of guidelines established by a school to ensure that all communication among educators, students, and stakeholders remains professional, ethical, and effective.

Enhancement Plan

Program Enhancement Plan						
KEY RESULT AREAS	OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES / INTERVENTIONS (STRATEGIES)	PERSONS INVOLVED	TIMELINE	BUDGET / RESOURCES NEEDED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
1. Clarity and Effectiveness in Teaching Communication	Ensure teachers provide clear and structured lessons.	Training on simplifying complex topics.	Teachers, Head Teachers	Year-Round	School Fund	Improved student comprehension and engagement.
	Minimize miscommunication in classroom instruction.	Use of structured lesson planning techniques.			Personal Fund	Clearer classroom instructions.
	Enhance teachers' use of instructional media.	Workshops on effective use of visuals and multimedia.			School Fund	Increased student engagement and understanding.
	Peer evaluations and feedback on clarity.	Feedback sessions and classroom observation.			Personal Fund	Increased instructional effectiveness.
2. Active Listening and Empathy in Communication	Improve teachers' ability to understand students' needs.	Conduct active listening workshops.	Teachers, Head Teachers	Year-Round	School Fund	More positive teacher-student relationships.
	Strengthen teacher-student relationships.	Encourage student feedback on teacher communication.			Personal Fund	Increased student trust and participation.
	Enhance empathy in interactions.	Empathy training and role-playing scenarios.			School Fund	Improved classroom climate.
	Implement teacher-student mentorship programs.	Assign teacher-mentors to selected students.			Personal Fund	Increased support and guidance for students.

Enhancement Plan

3. Collaboration and Team Communication	Promote teamwork among teachers for better school operations.	Team-building exercises on collaboration.	Teachers, Head Teachers	Year-Round	School Fund	Stronger teamwork and coordination.
	Improve communication in department meetings.	Regular discussion forums for teachers.			Personal Fund	More effective and efficient meetings.
	Improve cross-level communication (e.g. primary to secondary).	Inter-grade level meetings and collaboration projects.			School Fund	Better continuity in instruction.
	Conflict resolution training.	Conflict management seminars or workshops.			Personal Fund	Reduced interpersonal conflicts.
4. Professional and Ethical Responsibility in Communication	Ensure teachers maintain professionalism.	Workshops on ethical speech and writing.	Teachers, Head Teachers	Year-Round	School Fund	Reduced communication conflicts.
	Foster responsible communication.	Development of a school-wide communication code of conduct.			Personal Fund	More respectful and responsible interactions.
	Build digital professionalism.	Training on responsible use of social media and email.			School Fund	Professional digital interactions.
	Strengthen stakeholder engagement.	Communication workshops for engaging parents and community.			School & Community Fund	Improved home-school partnerships.

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Enhancement
Program

**Leading with
Impact:**

Communication Mastery

for School Heads

DATE
TIME

PLACE
VENUE

Angela Fae C. Santiago

Enhancement Program

Programme Rationale:

Effective communication is essential for school heads, as it shapes school culture, fosters collaboration, and ensures smooth operations. Assistant Principals and Principals must communicate with clarity, responsibility, empathy, and professionalism to build trust among teachers, students, and parents. This program aims to enhance their leadership communication skills by promoting strategic messaging, conflict resolution, and ethical communication. By strengthening these skills, school heads can improve decision-making, address challenges effectively, and create a supportive learning environment that enhances both teacher performance and student success.

Definition of Terms

- Leadership Communication – The ability of school heads to convey clear, strategic, and inspiring messages that align with school goals and policies.
- Clarity in Leadership Communication – The practice of providing transparent, direct, and well-structured information to teachers, students, and stakeholders.
- Responsibility in Communication – The accountability of school leaders in ensuring their communication fosters trust, fairness, and ethical decision-making.
- Conflict Resolution – Strategies used by school heads to mediate disputes and foster productive dialogue among stakeholders.
- Professional Communication Ethics – The principles guiding school heads to communicate respectfully, confidentially, and with integrity in all professional interactions.

Enhancement Plan

KEY RESULT AREAS	OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES/INTERVENTIONS (STRATEGIES)	PERSONS INVOLVED	TIMELINE	BUDGET or RESOURCES NEEDED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
1. Clarity and Effectiveness in Teaching Communication	- Ensure teachers provide clear and structured lessons. - Minimize miscommunication in classroom instruction.	- Training on simplifying complex topics. - Use of structured lesson planning techniques. - Peer evaluations and feedback on clarity.	- Teachers - Head Teachers	Year-Round	- School Fund - Personal Fund	- Improved student comprehension and engagement - Clearer classroom instructions.
2. Active Listening and Empathy in Communication	- Improve teachers' ability to understand students' needs. - Strengthen teacher-student relationships through better listening skills.	- Conduct active listening workshops. - Encourage student feedback on teacher communication. - Implement teacher-student mentorship programs.	- Teachers - Head Teachers	Year-Round	- School Fund - Personal Fund	- More positive teacher-student relationships. - Increased student trust and participation.
3. Collaboration and Team Communication	- Promote teamwork among teachers for better school operations. - Improve communication in department meetings.	- Team-building exercises on collaboration. - Regular discussion forums for teachers. - Conflict resolution training.	- Teachers - Head Teachers	Year-Round	- School Fund - Personal Fund	- Stronger teamwork and coordination. - More effective and efficient meetings.
4. Professional and Ethical Responsibility in Communication	- Ensure teachers maintain professionalism in their communication. - Foster ethical and responsible communication with students.	- Workshops on ethical speech and writing. - Development of a school-wide communication code of conduct.	- Teachers - Head Teachers	Year-Round	- School Fund - Personal Fund	- Reduced communication conflicts. - More respectful and responsible interactions.

Enhancement Plan

	colleagues, and parents.					
5. Strategic Leadership Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strengthen the ability to communicate vision and goals effectively. - Improve speech clarity when addressing teachers and stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public speaking training for school leadership. - Goal-setting workshops with clear messaging techniques. - Regular feedback from teachers on leadership communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assistant Principal - Principal 	Year-Round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Fund - Personal Fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clearer communication of school goals and policies. - More engaged and aligned teaching staff.
6. Conflict Resolution and Crisis Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance leadership's ability to manage conflicts professionally. - Ensure transparent communication during crises. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conflict management training. - Crisis communication planning workshops. - Role-playing exercises for handling difficult conversations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assistant Principal - Principal 	Year-Round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Fund - Personal Fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced staff and student conflicts. - More effective crisis handling.
7. Decision-Making and Policy Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve transparency in decision-making communication. - Ensure policies are communicated clearly to all stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leadership workshops on clear decision communication. - Implementation of structured policy announcements. - Regular school-wide briefings for updates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assistant Principal - Principal 	Year-Round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Fund - Personal Fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased staff understanding and compliance with policies. - More informed decision-making across departments
8. Building a Culture of Open and Inclusive Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote a school environment where communication is open and inclusive. - Encourage a two-way dialogue to leadership and staff. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open forums for teacher feedback. - Implementation of anonymous feedback systems. - Leadership training on active listening and response. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assistant Principal - Principal 	Year-Round	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School Fund - Personal Fund 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher teacher satisfaction with leadership communication. - More inclusive decision-making processes.

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Conclusions

The study starts with the problem, and the conclusions drawn from the results for the study were based on the null hypothesis:

1. The findings indicate that both teachers and school heads exhibit a high level of leadership communication, characterized by clarity, depth, care, and responsibility. Teachers demonstrated more consistent communication practices, while school heads also maintained strong communication with slight variations in approach. The overall results reflect a shared commitment to effective and meaningful communication, which fosters a positive, supportive, and collaborative school environment conducive to student and staff success. However, there remains room for improvement in addressing communication lapses.
2. In terms of student academic performance, the results indicate overall improvement, particularly in the Outstanding and Very Satisfactory categories. However, the uneven distribution of performance across grading periods suggests the need for further investigation and targeted interventions.
3. A statistically difference exists between the leadership communication levels of teachers and school heads, as shown by the Mann-Whitney U test. This suggests variations in how leadership communication is perceived or practiced across different roles.
4. Also, the correlation analysis shows no relationship between leadership communication and student academic performance. This implies that while effective communication is essential in school leadership, other factors may have a stronger influence on student outcomes.
5. The findings underscore the vital role of leadership communication in influencing student academic performance. It was concluded that clear, responsible, and collaborative communication among teachers, head teachers, assistant principals, and principals is essential for creating a positive and high-performing educational environment. The study affirms that establishing a Leadership Communication Enhancement Program is not only beneficial but necessary for achieving sustainable improvements in leadership practices and student outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings given and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Schools should provide targeted training for school heads to improve clarity, empathy, and accountability. Encouraging collaboration between teachers and leaders, using tools like self-assessments and peer feedback, and promoting open

feedback from staff and students can enhance communication. Regular reviews should be done to track progress.

2. Schools should analyze why student performance varies across grading periods. Identifying weak points can help tailor interventions, improve lesson planning, and boost student engagement. Ongoing monitoring and data use are key to maintaining academic growth.
3. To bridge communication gaps between teachers and leaders, schools should offer leadership coaching, joint meetings, and open forums. As leadership communication showed no direct link to academic performance, future research should examine other contributing factors like teaching methods and student motivation.
4. Future studies should include more diverse schools and adopt mixed methods (quantitative and qualitative) to gain deeper insights. Objective tools should be used to assess communication levels, and school leaders should also evaluate teachers' communication to provide a fuller picture.
5. Lastly, Schools should launch a structured communication development program for all leaders, focusing on clear messaging and collaborative leadership. Regular feedback and assessments should be built to ensure continuous improvement and a positive impact on student outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study complies with Republic Act No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, to ensure the protection of personal data collected from participants. Informed consent will be obtained from all respondents, clearly outlining the purpose of the study, the type of data to be collected, and how it will be used.

Participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and respondents may withdraw at any time without consequences. To maintain confidentiality and anonymity, all responses will be kept strictly confidential, and no personally identifiable information will be disclosed. Data will be securely stored, with digital files being password-protected and printed documents kept in a locked cabinet to prevent unauthorized access.

The researcher will ensure that collected data is retained only for the necessary duration required for research analysis, after which it will be securely deleted or disposed of. Additionally, the study will strictly adhere to institutional research ethics policies and legal guidelines on data protection. By implementing these measures, the researcher upholds ethical research standards and safeguards the rights and privacy of all participants.

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